

PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS OF THE USE OF COACHING TECHNOLOGY IN THE FORMATION OF SPIRITUAL EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE IN STUDENTS

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Annotation: At the present stage of reforming the system of higher education, there is a need to search for new modern technologies for managing the training and education of future teachers. The higher school makes high demands not only on the special training of a graduate of a pedagogical university (knowledge of the subject and teaching methods), but also on the assessment of his personal qualities and achievements. The readiness for self-development, the development of new equipment, technologies, and methods of work come first. In this regard, one of the promising areas of individualization of higher pedagogical education, which is based on the disclosure of the student's personal potential and abilities, is coaching.

Keywords: Coaching technology, method, quality, student, psychological factors.

There are several definitions of coaching and each of them reflects one of its facets. Let's highlight the main ones:

Coaching is a method of unlocking a person's potential in order to maximize their work (John Whitmore)¹.

Coaching is a systemic result-oriented process in which a person promotes change through self-learning (Anthony Grant)².

Coaching is an art that assists in enhancing the learning and development of another person (Miles Downey)³.

In recent years, coaching has been called the technology of revealing a person's internal resources. The main goal of coaching is to increase the effectiveness in personal and professional areas of activity. For a more complete disclosure of the concept of coaching, consider the main coaching models: "Grow" and "Valor".

The Grow model is a method of setting and achieving goals, as well as problem solving. Many specialists were involved in the development of the model, but the greatest contribution was made by: A. Graham, A. Fine and D. Whitmore.

Translated from English, "Grow" means "Growth", while comprehending the growth of oneself as a person. The abbreviation of the coaching model conditionally consists of stimulating words: goals, reality, options, will (goal, reality, opportunity, intentions).

The coaching model "Grow" consists of four stages of revealing the internal reserves of a person:

Stage 1 - "Goals"

¹ Whitmore J. High performance coaching. / Per. from English. - M.: International Academy of Corporate Governance and Business, 2005.

² Baranova O. I. Coaching technology as a way to form the skills of co-management of learning among students - future primary school teachers and younger students // Scientific and methodological electronic journal "Concept". - 2015. - T. 9. - S. 6–10. – URL: <http://e-koncept.ru/2015/95018.htm>

³ Graham W. Group psychoanalytic coaching. [Electronic resource]. URL: <https://www.hse.ru/ma/psyan/reportage/graham>

At this stage, a model of the predicted result of the activity and ways to achieve it are proposed. When setting a goal, it is recommended to use the basic tools of coaching, namely the three planning questions that help uncover intrinsic motivation.

1. What do you expect?
2. What is important to you at the moment?
3. How do you plan to achieve the result?

Stage 2 - "Reality"

At this stage, there is an awareness of how to achieve the desired result, and a path is built along which it is necessary to move towards the intended goal. For a deeper understanding, it is recommended to examine the current situation with the help of the following questions:

1. What is my current situation?
2. What barriers are preventing me from taking action?
3. What resources can I use to solve the problem?

Stage 3 - "Options"

This stage is characterized by the definition of a strategy for further actions in removing the obstacle. To develop it, the coach (trainer, teacher) recommends using the following questions:

- What can I do to solve the problem?
- What options can I consider?
- Who will help me with this task?
- What experience do I have in successfully dealing with situations like this? What was the plan then?
- Perhaps my friend has already solved a similar situation?
- Which of the solutions should be chosen?

Stage 4 - "Will"

At the final stage, we work out solutions, creating an action plan to achieve the goal, answering the following questions:

4. What is the first step I should take?
5. How long will it take for me to complete it?
6. What obstacles await me, and can I anticipate and eliminate them?
7. Who among the people around me can help and support me?

The sequence of actions in the "Grow" model is cyclical and develops in a spiral, this is due to the problem of specifying the goal. Refinement of the goal is allowed until the current situation is examined in detail (the stage of reality). Having completed this action, it is necessary to return to the first stage and set the goal more accurately. Sometimes there are situations when, at first glance, a correctly set initial goal may turn out to be impossible and inappropriate after analyzing the situation (the stage of reality). When reviewing the list of possibilities and intent, it is important to double-check how well they fit the intended purpose.

Rick Paddock in his book "Your Life Navigator" presented his vision of the coaching model and called it "Valor". And the decoding of the abbreviation is as follows:

V - vision;

A - awareness (awareness); L - love;

O - obstacle (obstacle); R - result.

Let's take a closer look at each of the steps:

"Vision"

Vision is based on two components. The first forms the conceptual basis of actions and acts as a guide. The second component is the emotional component, which contains a motivational stimulus. Thus, the vision lies in the fact that, based on the understanding of the key idea, to present perspectives and timely eliminate emerging difficulties (problems).

"Awareness"

This step is aimed at the readiness to select, analyze and assimilate information, determining its value and significance in accordance with the vision of the problem. Awareness is the main component in coaching, it ensures focus and clarity of results⁴.

"Love"

Bert Hellinger, the author of the method of system constellations, believes that everything in the world is done out of love. At this stage, there is an explanation of issues related to the attitude towards oneself and others.

"Obstacles"

This step is designed to help assess what is happening and choose the right path to achieve the goal. Often people "carry within themselves" internal psychological problems that prevent them from making the right choice. The author identifies two leading factors that influence decision making: "the limits of our environment" and "false authorities". In solving the problem of removing obstacles, the author recommends based on his personal preferences and using the approach: I am realized in what is closer to me.

"Result"

The basis of this step is the readiness to assess the situation and make the right choice.

Thus, coaching is a special technology of individual work, which is based on the preferences of the individual, his priorities and capabilities.

Summing up, we can draw conclusions: coaching is a technology that combines various modern methods and techniques. It helps the teacher to motivate the student to the correct planning of his education and directs him to self-realization and development of his personality.

The advantage of coaching technology is that it not only promotes learning, but also activates and motivates the student in self-learning and self-development. With the help of coaching technology, students develop non-standard thinking, which leads to individual and personal development and the formation of responsibility for their choice.

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